

Support For Tenancy and Recovery Targets Project (START): Evaluation Report

Executive Summary

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Executive Summary

In my role as Head of Service, South East Community Healthcare (SECH) Mental Health Service, I am delighted to provide a foreword in relation to this evaluation report of the START programme. START (Support for Tenancy And Recovery Targets) was developed as a floating support model for mental health Service Users to access and sustain housing through the Local Authorities or identified Approved Housing Bodies, with support from a Housing Support Worker. The support element was funded initially by SECH's Mental Health Service Reform Fund (SRF). Dr Suzanne Denieffe and her research team in Waterford Institute of Technology were then commissioned by the SRF team in SECH to conduct an independent evaluation of this new and innovative programme.

START is a collaboration and partnership between the HSE Mental Health Service and SRF in SECH, the five Local Authorities in the South East and two Approved Housing Bodies, the Good Shepherd Centre in Kilkenny and Focus Ireland. It is a person centred and rights based model. The partnership approach it adopts has been recommended in both the *National Housing Strategy for Disabled People, 2022-2027* and *Sharing The Vision, A Mental Health Policy for Everyone, Department of Health, 2020*.

This evaluation is an excellent and thorough report that portrays the perspectives of the key stakeholders involved with START: Service Users, multidisciplinary staff in SECH Community Mental Health and Rehabilitation and Recovery teams, staff in the Local Authority Housing Departments, managers from the HSE, Approved Housing Bodies and the START Support Workers. It highlights the success of the partnership approach, and it is particularly heartening to note that thirty five Service Users have accessed and maintained individual supported housing tenancies since September 2019. Service Users have described the positive impacts the independent tenancies have had on their lives, and this is a testament to the good work that is being done by the Support Workers and to the motivation and commitment of all those involved with START. The programme continues to have successful outcomes despite the challenges presented by the COVID pandemic.

I would like to acknowledge the direction and commitment of the Project Manager for Housing Coordination, Anne Barrett, and the SRF Programme Manager, Dr. Sheila Kissane, for the vision to develop START as a pathway to address the housing needs of our mental health Service Users. I also wish to acknowledge the work of each and every individual and group who have contributed in any way to its continued success.

Many thanks to those involved for allowing their work to be objectively evaluated, with a view to learning from and making improvements to the START programme. Particular thanks to the research team in Waterford Institute of Technology for their work and attention to detail at every stage in this evaluation.

It is hoped that START will be supported on a long-term basis and be adapted as needed so that it can continue to be successfully embedded in the Mental Health Service.

David Heffernan

Head of Mental Health Services
South East Community Healthcare

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A special thanks to all who participated in the surveys and interviews. This evaluation was entirely dependent on their good will. The Service Users’ contribution in this regard was invaluable. Siobhan Turner and Gerry Maley, General Managers for SECH’s Mental Health Services, acted as gatekeepers for the research involved in this evaluation. For this, and for their ongoing commitment to the work of START we would like to thank them. The support of David Heffernan, Head of Service, throughout the development and evaluation of START has been critical to its success.

The work of the SRF team, led by Sheila Kissane, in supporting both the implementation of START, and its evaluation, has been crucial to the development of this report.

John McCusker from the National Office for Service User Engagement, Sharon Lane, who worked with Genio, and Orla Barry all played a part in supporting Anne Barrett, Project Manager for Housing Coordination in driving this project from its infancy as a mere idea, to its reality of housing with support for those who can now live independently.

Background to the Project

The Service Reform Fund (SRF) was created by the Department of Health, the Department of Housing, Planning, and Local Government, the Health Service Executive Ireland (HSE), Local Authorities and the Atlantic Philanthropies, in collaboration with Genio, to implement service reform in Ireland in relation to mental health, disability and homelessness. The community living stream with the SRF fund focuses on optimising opportunities for mental health Service Users to live in their own homes and to provide person-centred supports to maximise independence, autonomy, and connectedness in the community.

The Mental Health Services have an interest in developing “a whole systems approach to recovery from mental illness that maximises an individual’s quality of life and social inclusion and encourages their skills, promoting independence and autonomy to give them hope for the future and leads to successful community living through appropriate support” (Killaspy et al., 2005, p.163). People with ongoing mental health difficulties have the right to live independently, be included in the community and have equal access to public housing programmes, as outlined in Articles 19 and 28d of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations, 2006). The National Housing Strategy for People with Disabilities, 2011-2016 (Department of the Environment, Community and Local Government) also promoted access to housing and support to live independently. This was affirmed in Rebuilding Ireland (Government of Ireland, 2016), and Housing for All- a New Housing Plan for Ireland (Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, 2021), with more recent commitments to fulfil these aims outlined in the new National Housing Strategy for Disabled People, 2022-2027 (Government of Ireland, 2022).

‘Housing support’ is seen as separate to clinical mental health support, with a focus on enabling someone to manage on a day-to-day basis whilst they are living in their own home and to become part of their own local community. Where it exists, this type of support is usually provided by a voluntary agency, which works in partnership with Service Users, mental health services and housing providers. Support workers assist Service Users to transition from institutional settings or other unsuitable environments, which may present risks of homelessness, to independent living in mainstream housing. In some instances, they or an approved housing body and or local authority may work with Service Users to identify suitable and secure housing and to address issues linked to support needs that may put a tenancy at risk. This type of model is usually referred to as ‘floating support’.

Ensuring people with mental health difficulties have access to housing and support to live independently is also a key part of their recovery and rehabilitation; having somewhere to live is essential to recovery (HSE’s National Framework for Recovery in Mental Health, 2018-2020). The START programme was therefore developed to provide Service Users with an opportunity to create a home, become part of a local community and engage with the services which enable their

Different terms are used depending on the service, agency and context, for example client, customer, tenant or service user. For the purpose of this evaluation, the term service user will be used as it reflects that the person is a user of the START Project services.

recovery. It adopts an interagency collaborative approach to supporting Service Users access and maintain secure tenancies, as recommended in Vision for Change (Department of Health, 2006, p. 109) and Sharing the Vision, A Mental Health Policy for Everyone' (Department of Health, 2020, Recommendations 66-69).

The overall aim of the START Project is to provide and/or sustain secure tenancies with support for mental health Service Users with identified housing needs.

The START Project objectives are:

To promote recovery of Service Users; the long-term aim is that Service Users become more active citizens in their everyday life, thereby achieving improved overall health and wellbeing outcomes.

To develop an evidence-based sustainable model of practice which becomes embedded in future service delivery. Such a model will address issues which are thwarting equality of access to housing.

Establishment of the START Project

Programme Managers for Housing Coordination (PMHCs) were employed in each CHO area in 2018 as part of the Service Reform Fund initiative to support the implementation of the National Housing Strategy for People with Disabilities (NHSPD), as it applied to people with mental health issues. In SECH/CHO5, the PMHC was recruited on a part-time basis through the Service Reform Fund in October 2018. In Quarter 1 of 2019, the PMHC consulted with each of the Mental Health Social Work teams, given their longstanding role in relation to housing advocacy. The Social Workers subsequently forwarded their data on the specific housing and support needs of Service Users throughout CHO5. This data was analysed and formatted by an SRF funded researcher in WIT, and informed a business case for SRF funding for the START Project.

SRF funding was granted for the equivalent of three Mental Health Housing Support Workers (qualified as Social Care Workers) to provide specialist support across two or more Local Authority areas for defined time periods. This was dependent on the capacity of Local Authorities to provide secure tenancies to identified mental health Service Users whose needs were within the scope of this project.

The PMHC and SRF Programme Manager approached each of the SEOs in the housing departments of the five Local Authorities and presented a proposal for START, outlining its fit with the aims of the National Housing Strategy for People with Disabilities. All five Local Authorities and two Approved Housing Bodies expressed an interest in the proposed partnership, and four Local Authorities indicated a readiness to commence, giving a commitment to providing or financing a number of suitable properties.

The Housing Support service was tendered for and awarded to voluntary service providers; the

Good Shepherd Centre in Kilkenny and to Focus Ireland in Counties Carlow, Tipperary (South), and Wexford. Service Level Agreements and confidentiality agreements were subsequently agreed between HSE management and these two Approved Housing Bodies.

START Project Implementation

The START project model can be summarised as follows:

- Oversight is provided via an HSE-led Steering Committee
- Referrals are made via Community Mental Health Teams
- Housing is sourced primarily via Local Authorities and Approved Housing Bodies.
- A Housing Support Worker is employed by the Approved Housing Body and works collaboratively with the Service User and key members of his/her Community Mental Health Team

Oversight

Representatives of the HSE Mental Health Services in SECH /CHO5, the Approved Housing Bodies and the Local Authorities have collaborated in developing an interagency START Steering Group for each county. In four counties, there is Service User representation. Each group is chaired by the Project Manager for Housing Coordination in the Mental Health Services. It meets once every quarter or as often as required. Each group agrees Standard Operational Procedures (SOPs), and Terms of Reference (TORs). The SECH's Housing Implementation Group (HIG), the board of the AHB and the relevant Housing Disability Steering Groups are advised of the deliberations of this group and consulted as required.

Referrals

Every referral is agreed with the Service User and with his/her Community Mental Health Team. A preliminary profile form is then completed by the social worker or identified MDT member and discussed with the Social Work Team Leader and the Project Manager for Housing Coordination to check the criteria (as specified in the SOPs) is met. A fuller assessment form is then completed in collaboration with the service user, who signs a consent section in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulations. Each Local Authority area hosts an Allocations Advisory Group, where the information on these forms is reviewed by at least one representative from the Local Authority, the AHB and the Mental Health Services. Information on the location, type and size of the properties available for the programme is shared and after discussion, recommendations for nominations are submitted to each Council's nomination officer. The Local Authority then follows its own processes to make final allocation decisions.

Housing

Most housing required by the project is accommodation with one or two bedrooms. It must be of a standard approved by the Local Authorities and in locations which are accessible to amenities and services, and where Service Users feel safe. In Kilkenny, all housing for the START project is supplied by the Good Shepherd Centre, usually purchased with CASS funding. In the three other Local

Authority areas it is a mix of Local Authority and AHB housing acquired through the CASS scheme.

Housing Support Worker

The Housing Support Worker supports the Service Users to define and achieve their own recovery goals as they relate to independent living. S/he acts in a key-working capacity using a case management approach. Support is provided in three key phases: (1) Preparing to move (2) Moving and settling in and (3) Becoming independent. The support work involves close collaborative working with members of the Service Users' Community Mental Health Teams and housing providers. Shared Support Meetings are held with the Service User and key personnel to agree actions and timelines.

The support service provided by START Support Workers funded initially by the SRF, and employed by the Good Shepherd Centre in Kilkenny and by Focus Ireland in counties Carlow, Tipperary (South), and Wexford has continued during the time of the evaluation.

START Project Outcomes to Time of Report

Outcomes per county:

- Establishment of Steering Groups
- Recruitment of Support Workers
- Allocations of housing and support
- Ongoing arrangements

Kilkenny

In July 2019, START in Kilkenny held its first Interagency Steering Group and the Good Shepherd Centre recruited its full-time START Support Worker. A total of fourteen allocations with support were made in Kilkenny between September 2019 and June 2021; One additional Service User was supported to sustain his tenancy.

Tipperary

In December 2019, START in Tipperary held its first interagency Steering Group and in February 2020, Focus Ireland recruited a part-time START Support Worker, but the person in role moved post in April 2021. Focus Ireland then allocated those Service Users requiring ongoing support to a Tenancy Support Worker as an interim arrangement. Seven individuals were allocated six properties with support, with two siblings sharing their tenancy.

Carlow

Carlow and South Tipperary combined its START Steering Groups. In Carlow, the full-time START Support Worker commenced in May 2020, and left following the cessation of funding in May 2021. During this period, five Service Users were allocated housing with support. An additional individual was supported in preparation for their tenancy, and has since been allocated a suitable property.

Focus Ireland has allocated those Service Users requiring ongoing support to a Housing Support Worker as an interim arrangement. The Senior Housing Support Worker/Team Lead devoted half their time to supervision and management of the other two Focus Ireland Support Workers; a different SRF funding stream was used to finance this arrangement.

Wexford

Wexford held its first START Steering Group in February 2020, and a full-time START Housing Support Worker was employed from June 2020 to May 2021. During that period six Service Users were housed by the Local Authority, and a further five engaged with the Support Worker with a view to taking up forthcoming allocations in properties which would be later acquired by Focus Ireland. There was a delay in this due to COVID restrictions, but two Service Users have since been housed in Focus Ireland properties. Three Service Users still await a housing allocation. Focus Ireland has acquired an additional property, and one allocation is imminent. They have committed to the purchase of a further three properties, which will be allocated in due course. Focus Ireland has allocated those Service Users requiring ongoing support to a Housing Support Worker as an interim arrangement.

To date of report, the START Project has successfully obtained and secured tenancies with support for thirty-five Mental Health Service Users throughout the SECH region. A further five Service Users have been supported to prepare for or sustain tenancies.

Research Evaluation Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research was to examine and evaluate the START project from a multi-stakeholder perspective to inform the roll out of future ‘floating support’ housing projects.

The research objectives were:

1. To examine views of the stakeholders on the structures, processes and outcomes of the START Project.
2. To explore Service Users’ views of their participation in the START Project in relation to housing stability and satisfaction, service access, mental and physical health, social connections, community participation and quality of life.
3. To make recommendations to inform future implementation of Floating Housing Support projects.

Evaluation Methodology

The START Project was evaluated using a case study with mixed methods design. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Regional HSE Research Ethics Committee and the Waterford Institute of Technology Research Ethics Committee.

Online questionnaires were distributed to staff (n=60; response rate 43%) from the SECH Mental Health Services, Local Authorities and Approved Housing Bodies involved in the START Project. These questionnaires explored, from a multi-stakeholder perspective, views on the START Project to inform and improve the roll out of future floating support housing projects.

Questionnaires were also distributed to the START Project Service Users (n =33), who were sent a postal questionnaire. Twenty-three questionnaires were returned (response rate 70%). These questionnaires explored socio-demographic factors, clinical information, and service users' views on their experiences of previous and current accommodation.

START Project Service Users were also invited to take part in an individual semi-structured telephone interview to explore their views on the START Project. Nine agreed to be interviewed (27%).

Summary of Findings

The findings include the results from the stakeholders' questionnaires, Service User questionnaires and Service User interviews. Each of these will now be presented.

Stakeholder Findings

Four separate stakeholder specific surveys were administered to staff involved in the START Project (n =60). These included Health Service Executive Multi-Disciplinary Team (MDT) members who supported Service Users, Local Authority/ County Council staff and staff from the Approved Housing Bodies working with the START Project including the Housing Support Workers. Of these, a total of thirty-six surveys were completed (response rate: 60%); breakdown as follows: HSE MDT staff (n=24); Local Authority /County Council (n=5); Approved Housing Body (n=7).

These completed questionnaires identified a number of key themes / findings and these are summarised below under the headings, structure, processes, outcomes and perceived challenges.

Structures in place to support START Programme

Overall, it was reported that the START Project enabled a means of collaboration between Local Authorities/County Councils, Approved Housing Bodies and the SECH MDTs; this was described as an effective collaborative working approach. It was further reported that there was a 'willingness from all partner agencies to make the START Programme work' with a 'shared vision' and 'commitment' to 'secure, obtain, maintain and sustain tenancies for the START Project participants.'

It was recognised that there needs to be continued and further interagency collaboration and cooperation to build agency buy-in in the future; commitment from all parties is required to facilitate a collaborative working model.

As the START Project develops further, it was also recognised that SECH areas will see an increase in demand and more referrals will be identified. Security of funding on a permanent basis was deemed 'essential' for the sustainment of the START Project; ongoing funding for housing units, Housing Support Workers, and an HSE Housing Coordination Manager is required for the future roll out of the START Project. It was reported that the withdrawal of supports, particularly support from the Housing Support Workers upon project completion, could result in a deterioration in some Service Users' mental health and increase the risk of tenancy breakdown.

The need for increased housing for START was identified, as was the need for additional support staff. It was felt that the current time awarded to Housing Support Workers posts was insufficient to meet the needs of Service Users, particularly where there were specific mental health challenges impacting on their tenancies.

Processes in place to support the START Programme

(i) The working processes of the START Project

The majority of respondents (n=24; 92%) were either 'somewhat', 'very' or 'completely' satisfied with the current working processes of the START Project and eighty-eight per cent (n =23) reported their role in the Project went 'as expected'. Almost all (96%) reported that the START Project went 'better than expected' or 'exceeded expectations'. A minority (n=1; 4%) reported levels of dissatisfaction and these related specifically to the allocation process and lack of properties available for service users/ clients.

(ii) The START Project referral and appeals process

Eighteen respondents from HSE MDT and LA staff reported they had made referrals to the START Project. From these, it was seen that the majority (16/18) were 'happy' with the referral process, particularly as their referrals were accepted / approved for the START Project. There were however mixed views on the efficiency of the process, level of feedback on the referrals made including where referrals weren't accepted, the level of paperwork to be completed and the appeals process. Difficulties were reported in relation to communication on the appeals process where it seemed the Local Authority had different priorities that were reported to be contrary to the priorities of the professionals in the Mental Health Services.

(iii) Criteria for the START Project

The majority of respondents reported that the criteria for the START Project did not need to change. However, some respondents reported the need to broaden criteria to cater for more complex needs, for example homelessness, and the need to ascertain the Service User's willingness and capacity to engage i.e., to pay rent and abide to tenancy agreement and supports.

(iv) The allocations process

It seemed there were conflicting priorities amongst stakeholder groups in terms of allocation

of tenancies; referrals to the START Project from Mental Health Service may not meet the requirements for long-term accommodation set by the County Councils. County Councils/Local Authorities may prioritise Service Users according to length of time on waiting list over level/ nature of need as assessed by MDTs.

(v) Stakeholders' views on the START Project time frame

The main point made regarding the START Project time frame was the delay in allocation of housing units, along with delay in identifying and purchasing suitable properties. The knock-on effect of these meant delays in progressing referrals/ tenancies in some cases. However, most respondents were happy with the project timeframes (n=16; 70%).

(vii) Stakeholder engagement, in terms of project management

Most respondents were happy with the project management (n=21; 81%) and found the engagement effective, with a range of mediums utilised for this engagement. However, there were suggestions to further develop and improve communication amongst and across all stakeholder groups.

There was a reported 'blurring of boundaries' in relation to roles and functions at times. The stakeholders called for further development of a Shared Care Model. Respondents also called for the need to further develop communications to enhance the collaborative approach; the need to build on current working practices and communication and partnership working across and within stakeholder groups.

Outcomes: Service Providers' Overall Views of the START Project

The START Project was credited by the respondents with obtaining and securing housing with support for the twenty-nine Service Users who had, at the time of the questionnaire distribution, successfully transitioned to their START tenure as a result of participating in the START Project. According to the respondents, the Project has achieved positive outcomes for Service Users with mental health difficulties to live independently in the community.

The project was described as offering Service Users 'a place to call home' and support in obtaining, transitioning to and sustaining a tenancy with access to a Housing Support Worker as required; support was usually needed to address identified needs within specific time frames. The 'stability of housing' as described by stakeholders, supported Service Users to address their mental health issues, relieving some of the stressors around their mental health and further enhancing their recovery.

The project was also seen as reducing demands on the Adult Mental Health Services; prior to the START Project, some Service Users required admissions to the Department of Psychiatry (DOP) or Adult Mental Health Group Homes or remained within institutional care settings. It was believed

that the START Project reduced or prevented homelessness amongst some Service Users; ninety-four percent of the START programme participants had been identified at risk of homelessness prior to their transition onto the programme.

Levels of engagement with the MHS were reported as having 'decreased' with a reported 'significant shift' in Service User engagement to 'needs based' engagement. The role of Housing Support Workers was perceived by MDT participants as having a major part to play in addressing the needs of the Service Users. MDT members reported that their engagement with Housing Support Workers involved meeting them together with the Service Users at MDT meetings, during Outreach Team visits for medication management, or to discuss or implement care or support plans with Social Work staff.

The START Project was viewed as having established a working model of practice; offering an alternative model to the traditional HSE model used to support Service Users with mental health challenges to obtain and sustain their own tenancies.

The person-centred ethos and approach adopted by the START Project was practised through the nature of support given to the Service Users, which promoted the development of their independent living skills. The respondents perceived that the START Project enabled the Service Users to make informed choices; from the initial discussions and consultations regarding the Project (choice of being put forward for referral or not) to the identification of supports required to prepare for and sustain their tenancy. This was seen as 'reversing the power of dynamics'; with the Service User 'accessing' independent accommodation rather than the services arranging or 'directing' the individual towards shared HSE hostel accommodation identified by the MHS. Therefore, the START Project facilitated and empowered Service Users to live independently in the community. Stakeholders believed that they supported and responded to the needs of Service Users through advocacy, 'being their advocate or voice' throughout the START process.

The START Programme's role in 'fostering independence' amongst Service Users was recognised in the development of their independent living / life skills. These included the development of budgeting skills, a routine and structure to their daily lives, links within the community and access to education and employment. Support in their own homes was valued, having an impact on their understanding of how recovery can enhance their personal lives; developing independence through support in achieving life goals was articulated as leading to 'improved confidence', resulting in more stable mental health.

START Project Perceived Challenges

Limited or a lack of housing stock was seen as presenting a major challenge for further project development and in establishing future floating housing support models. Service Users were deemed eligible but could not be referred due to lack of housing stock. This then affected service

users' expectations of the programme.

The respondents reported having received very little or no training in relation to the organisational functions of each stakeholder group. The provision of specific training for all stakeholder groups to reflect remit, criteria, processes and function of each organisation was recommended.

Challenges were reported that related to individual tenancy sustainment, including assessment, allocation, moving in and sustaining tenancies. These included dealing with issues/ concerns that may affect eligibility for housing, such as past convictions as a minor; challenges in moving to a new area/ community to live independently; cultural beliefs; practical issues such as form filling, not understanding Social Welfare entitlements, dealing with County Councils and the Department of Social Protection regarding furnishings/white goods, day-to-day routine and management of household tasks; emotional issues; feelings of not having a choice of accommodation, i.e. location of property.

Challenges were expressed by Local Authority/County Council and AHB Service Providers in relation to housing people with mental health difficulties. These included managing or maintaining properties in terms of budgeting, rent arrears and possible anti-social behaviour. The vulnerability of people with mental health difficulties as victims of anti-social behaviour, as well as transitioning to new communities with risk of social isolation were also seen as challenges. Going forward, the START Project should help the Service Users to develop stronger empathy with neighbours and an understanding of how their behaviour might affect others. They also expressed concern that supports be continued as required, as non-compliance with conditions of tenure may result in the Service User being discharged from the programme or losing their tenancy.

Some respondents reported that emerging challenges were dealt with in a supportive, understanding and sensitive manner; others reported that some challenges were ongoing, while other challenges remained unresolved. Levels of satisfaction in responding to presenting challenges were enhanced through ongoing consultation with all stakeholder groups.

Service User Findings

The START Project Service Users were invited to participate in this evaluation in two ways, via postal questionnaire and individual semi-structured telephone interview. All Service Users (n =33) were sent a postal questionnaire and twenty-three questionnaires were returned (response rate 70%) via stamped addressed envelopes to the research team. In total, fourteen (47%) service users agreed to participate in the interviews. A member of the research team contacted each Service User to arrange a suitable time and date for interview. However, due to difficulties in securing suitable times and dates for interview, five Service Users withdrew their consent, which led to a total of nine (27%) Service Users participating in the qualitative phase.

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Questionnaire Results

Of those who responded to the questionnaires, nine (40%) are female and fourteen (60%) are male. Age was reported in ranges, with sixteen (70%) aged between 25-44 years and seven (30%) between 44-64 years. Almost all were receiving the Department of Social Protection's Disability payment (92%), with one participant receiving Lone Parent allowance and another participant receiving a Back to Education payment.

With regard to employment, no Service Users were engaged with the employment support services, one person worked voluntary hours with a charity, and another Service User attended a mental health day centre.

Regarding mental health, all were aware of their mental health diagnosis. Only thirteen Service Users provided information on their mental health diagnosis. These included eating disorder-bulimia, bi-polar mood disorder, schizophrenia, depression and anxiety. Of those who identified that they had been hospitalised for mental health conditions (n =15), the length of time since last admission ranged from within the last month (2 Service Users), within the last year (1 Service User), eight had been admitted between one and three years ago, three more than three years ago. One Service User couldn't remember his/her last admission and the remaining Service User did not answer this element of the question.

Participants reported a range of physical health issues including fatigue, anaemia, bowel issues, diabetes and rheumatism. Service users were asked in an open-ended question to give their views on their previous and current (START) accommodation. Answers included positive and negative responses. Positive elements included living with family members or staff who cared for them, close to town or near work. Negative elements included feeling unwelcome or poor housing conditions. See Box 1 on next page.

Box 1. Service Users' views on previous accommodation

Views on Previous Accommodation: Good Elements	Views on Previous Accommodation: Bad Elements
<p>I had a little room of my own and it was in town, so I could get to work to earn some money to keep some independence.</p> <p>It was my family home and my daughters live there.</p> <p>Well looked after by nurses.</p> <p>The previous accommodation was better than the one prior to that.</p> <p>Excellent care with staff- nurses/ doctors.</p> <p>Close to town.</p> <p>Had a roof over my head.</p> <p>Good area, good neighbours.</p>	<p>Sharing with others. Drugs, hostile climate, sense of endangerment.</p> <p>I wasn't wanted or welcomed there. My housemates ignored me and didn't like me. I didn't want another house share where I would be unwelcome again.</p> <p>Not getting on with my family. Not enough space. I prefer to live on my own, independently.</p> <p>It wasn't independent.</p> <p>It was hard not having my own home and independence.</p> <p>Everything, it left me fearing for my life and I had no security. It wasn't a life, it was torture.</p> <p>High rent. Also, not sure about rent assistance.</p> <p>I was living in uninhabitable conditions and couldn't do daily household chores because of the condition of the property.</p> <p>It was shared accommodation. Lots of issues with people. House was freezing.</p> <p>Too big/ flight of stairs.</p> <p>Nothing, it was a dark hole that the only way I was getting out of it was in a body bag.</p> <p>Nothing good other than I was close to family.</p>

Service Users were also asked to rate their satisfaction with previous and current accommodation on a 1-10 scale, where 1 = completely dissatisfied and 10 = completely satisfied. For previous accommodation answers ranged from 1-10, mean 5.2. A small number, all of whom had come from HSE facilities/ housing, scored 8-10 for previous accommodation. For satisfaction with current accommodation, answers ranged from 5-10, mean 8.7.

When asked about satisfaction with current accommodation, one said they were somewhat satisfied, three were very satisfied while ten were completely satisfied. When asked about possible negative elements relating to their current accommodation, five Service Users said there were no bad elements, while two Service Users did not answer. See Box 2 below for detail on Service User views of current accommodation.

Box 2. Service Users’ views of current accommodation

Views on Current Accommodation: Good Elements	Views on Current Accommodation: Poor Elements
<p>Having my own space that I can control.</p> <p>The house is lovely. It is amazing. Lovely safe area - beautiful place/ home. I am welcome. It is okay to be myself - perfectly imperfect. I enjoyed making it my own. I have been upcycling furniture, which is brilliant as a distraction. I love the feeling of making a piece of furniture beautiful and unique. It is lovely to have my parents visit me, when lockdown permits.</p> <p>I feel safe and secure.</p> <p>The key worker is fantastic. I love being independent, the apartment and area is beautiful.</p> <p>Location.</p> <p>It has everything needed to maintain a comfortable standard of living.</p>	<p>The lack of insulation.</p> <p>One of my neighbours is sensitive to noise and bangs on the wall at me. It can be just having a shower/ drying my hair at 11am- or me exercising in my place. My support worker is aware of this. I try not to be too noisy and I make sure I exercise in daytime hours, and not too early or too late.</p> <p>No garden.</p> <p>The location, which is an internal problem only related to me.</p> <p>Not having a shed.</p> <p>Where I am.</p> <p>The neighbours.</p>

Box 2. Service Users' views of current accommodation (Cont.)

Views on Current Accommodation: Good Elements	Views on Current Accommodation: Poor Elements
<p>Everything - my home is perfect.</p> <p>I have a back garden for my dog, that she has her own place, and I can lock my door and not worry about someone breaking them in. I have a house where I can make it my home bit by bit. I've been given a chance at finally having a home and being able to live a life.</p> <p>Close to town and finished to a high standard. It is a new property and I have better communication with landlord for repairs or damages.</p> <p>I am in a very good part of town. It is mine and I don't have to deal with other people's problems anymore.</p> <p>Love where we live. No stairs, much warmer, security, and when any issues, always fixed.</p>	

Service User Interview Findings

Key reported reasons for referral to the programme included ongoing/ enduring mental health and accommodation needs, a willingness and determination to live independently, a lack of affordable housing options (such as the Housing Assistance Payment) and homelessness. Some Service Users reported negative experiences living in previous accommodation, which hastened their need for referral to START. These included unsafe living environments, histories of abusive relations, and inflexible housing policies and protocols leading to barriers to accessing housing.

Length of time living in current START accommodation, as reported by Service Users, ranged from approx. five months to one year and nine months.

Registered on Local Authority Housing List

The majority of Service Users (n=7/9; 78%) had previously been registered on the local authority housing list, with length of time ranging from six months prior to engaging with START to over eight years. For one Service User, they reported difficulty in registering with the Local Authority because of previous tenancy breaches. Two Service Users did not know, or did not indicate if they were registered on local authority housing list.

Tenancy Agreement

The majority of Service Users (n=8/9; 89%) reported having a tenancy agreement, with some detailing specific terms and conditions, for example;

“The tenancy agreement is very much like a financial agreement, in terms of support it says if anything goes wrong..., basically I can ring a number of the [AHB] and somebody will be out within a couple of weeks. Emergencies will be dealt with quicker. And then just pay my rent. I set up a Direct Debit at the start of the START Programme” (Service User 1);

“... [Tenancy agreement] is housing and support” (Service User 7);

“Tenancy agreement is housing only” (Service User 8).

Five Service Users reported that although they were aware that a tenancy agreement was in place; they were not sure of the specific details. However, all of these Service Users (n=5) acknowledged that they had been informed and agreed to the requirements of the tenancy agreement. One Service User reported that s/he did not have a tenancy agreement. However, caution is warranted when interpreting this finding as the Service User’s tone was quite hesitant when responding to the question.

Overall views of the START Programme

Service Users reported unanimously that their experiences of engaging with the START Programme were positive. Overall, high levels of satisfaction with the programme were reported and these reports were echoed throughout the findings, from initial referral stage to transitioning to START accommodation:

“I have no complaints about the START accommodation...Anything was a step up from [previous accommodation]” (Service User 1);

“...There is not one thing I could fault from beginning to end (Service User 2); I love it here, wouldn't change it for the world” (Service User 4).

Overall positive experiences of engagement were particularly evident when discussing their expectations of the programme *“...surpassed them [expectations] completely (Service User 2); “It [START] exceeded [expectations] like that kind of way”*. Significantly, all nine Service Users reported they would recommend START to others, and largely called for an increase in the programme capacity to cater for a greater number of mental health Service Users.

The majority of Service Users reported that they would like to sustain their START accommodation long-term; *“I hope that this will be like my forever home” (Service User 2); “I want to be here for life if possible” (Service User 4)*. Reasons for wanting to sustain long-term tenancies included feeling settled, content and comfortable in current accommodation/location with close proximity to family and children;

“I have a life for myself now where I am now” (Service User 3);

“I used to be running around at 90 miles an hour and you know getting nothing done only stressing out... but now [after START] I am more settled... I think the house [START accommodation] has helped me to settle ...” (Service User 8).

“Really good, a stable place to stay has made me way more confident, so it [confidence] has definitely improved” (Service User 6).

When Service Users were asked about the supports required to sustain long-term tenancies, some reported that support to manage their mental health coupled with daily living plans/ routines were essential:

“Keeping myself in good mental health. That's the key to all of this... is keeping myself well and keeping myself distracted with courses and things to do” (Service User 4).

However, three Service Users reported that they may consider a future move/transfer to an alternative independent living arrangement. Reasons for potential future move included a possible preference for a shared tenancy, or to upsize to accommodate a future partner/ family.

Provision of housing and support to obtain, transition and sustain independent living for mental health Service Users.

Service Users who engaged in the START Programme were seeking independent living or access to secure tenancies of their own and START was reported as enabling a sense of achievement in relation to this, aiding individual recovery. Service Users reported barriers to independent living in the absence of the START Programme: “...Without the programme I don’t know where I would be to be honest” (Service User 7). START was described as a “comprehensive programme” offering an accelerated route into housing for mental health service users. For this reason, the START Programme was credited for its role in the provision of housing and support to obtain, transition and sustain independent living for mental health. Service Users. It was reported that the START Programme afforded Service Users a “fresh start in life”, as it provided them with the opportunity to secure an independent tenancy with the necessary supports to live independently, something which may not have been possible without the START Programme.

Some Service Users acknowledged how “lucky” they were in terms of being accepted onto the programme, identifying the opportunity as a privilege as opposed to a right or entitlement.

Feelings of solidarity with others, who like them, were also reliant on services emerged from these discussions;

“I was lucky you know and there are probably more people in the same situation as me that aren’t so lucky [to get a place] but if there was hope out there because I couldn’t be more grateful, it [START] saved my life really” (Service User 2).

All Service Users reported a high level of satisfaction with the support they received in transitioning to the START Programme. They each reported that their “needs were met” by all involved in the Programme, and that this support was instrumental in facilitating a smooth transition to their new accommodation. Support received was described by some Service Users as “brilliant”: “...they did actually brilliant to be fair, any anxieties or queries that I had they would never make me like [feel like] it was silly or I shouldn’t feel that way” (Service User 2). From this, attention was drawn to the collaborative working approach adopted by the START Programme. Service Users reported that all organisations involved in START were working together for and on their behalf;

*“I think I was thoroughly supported. I couldn’t have asked for better...” (Service User 4)
“...multi-disciplinary team, OT (Occupational Therapist), the Community Mental Health Nurse, social worker, the community nurses, the key support, psychiatrists: they all worked*

well... the team... efficient communication, because of them [all START representatives] working well as a team it kind of bounced off me if you know what I'm saying. [I] felt supported and benefited from all members working collaboratively, very happy overall with all support received" (Service User 3).

In terms of family support, three Service Users reported that their families were actively involved throughout the transition process. These Service Users reported a satisfactory level of support from their families and they worked well with the wider START Team. However, two Service Users reported that although family were supportive, they were happy that the transition process was managed by the START Programme. Six other Service Users reported their families were not involved in their transition to the programme; four reported that they were satisfied / happy with that, with one other reporting that due to the quick transitioning process to the START tenancy, there wasn't a need for family involvement.

Some Service Users reported that they were extremely satisfied with their levels of engagement with their MDT and further referenced wider mental health supports received as accessible when required. Given the impact of COVID, some Service Users engaged online with members of their MDT and were satisfied with levels of engagement and support received.

Furthermore, the majority of Service Users reported not encountering a crisis since transitioning to the programme, but were aware of whom they could contact should a crisis arise:

"You have to look for it [support] you have to make the effort yourself but once its [support] its definitely there like... you have to make the first move you know [support in times of crisis] you have to go and make these things happens you know. You can't just sit around waiting for them but [MDT name] was always great to call and see how I was feeling but you have to make some kind of effort yourself" (Service User 8).

Transformative effects of the START Programme

The programme was described as transformative in terms of enabling Service Users by enhancing the emotional, financial, cognitive and physical resources needed to transition and sustain an independent tenancy; it aids recovery. On a number of occasions, Service Users referenced the START Programme as "life changing", and providing a "second chance in life". As mentioned earlier, in reasons for referral to the START Programme, Service Users had reported previously experiencing barriers to accessing housing. Some of these barriers were linked to a reported stigma associated with mental ill health;

"...because there's more people than me [requiring the START Programme]... And there's a lot of stigma attached to mental health, and especially then trying to get housing..." (Service User 4).

Other reported barriers included inflexible housing policies and protocols, and previous living arrangements. Some Service Users reported how the Programme reduced barriers to accessing housing; it enabled the recovery process and reduced the disabling effects of insecure housing and homelessness.

Examples of Service Users' quotes as they related to reported transformative experiences are reported below:

"I can't say enough good things about [START]. Everyone [involved in START] was great and helped me... it has changed my life and has been a great help. I just love it...the help I got and the information and the accommodation that I got connected with. The project (Support) worker was amazing and helped me so much. I couldn't have asked for anymore help" (Service User 6).

"[START] did a lot for me, and it will do so much for so many people like me, like it's finally given me a chance to have a life and to have a start and have what is going to be my forever home" (Service User 2).

Service Users, through their participation in the START Programme, reported a reduction of perceived support needs, which led to a lower and more appropriate level of engagement with their MDTs; more "stabilised" "improved" mental health amongst some Service Users was identified. One Service User encapsulated this: "well I had a lot of support at the start [HSE MDT]- e.g., OT (Occupational Therapy) but I didn't need that support [OT] then as time went on" (Service User 3). Others reported that they became more "settled" and developed a "routine", which led to a reduction in the need for MDT support;

"I used to go to chat with someone [Consultant Psychiatrist] every month [before participating in the START Programme] but now it is every 3 months...I am getting more settled and into more of a routine, so I suppose I am not contacting [the MDT] as much anymore since I'm in here [START accommodation] ... [The MDT] is delighted that I am getting on with life... like [START Programme] is after changing my life to be honest with you." (Service User 8).

The START Programme was acknowledged for enabling a sense of independence amongst Service Users: "I am much more independent...much, much more independent than what I was like... I have my own independence" (Service Users 3). "Now I feel fully independent and happy" (Service User 4).

Improvements in Service Users' well-being leading to improvements in their overall outlook and quality of life were described by some:

"[START Programme]...Really good and much better, it [positive outlook and increased quality of life] has definitely improved...the project has had a really positive impact on my life. I love it..." (Service User 6).

There was a clear sense of connectedness and involvement in the various stages of the START Programme, with Service Users describing feeling “understood”, “involved” and “reassured”.

Some Service Users reported they felt centrally involved in the decision-making process surrounding choice of accommodation and reported that the START Programme was reflective of their choices and individual needs; decisions about securing appropriate and suitably located accommodation received specific attention. There was a reported sense of equality in decision-making surrounding this process:

“I just wanted to take anything [accommodation]. But then they [START] were like reassuring me that I was better off to wait because they could find me [more suitable accommodation] ... [It turned out] I was better off waiting until I found a different place [location been the reason]... it [START Process] didn't feel rushed. I just felt like I was understood better, like it [START accommodation] wasn't the first place [option I was offered] and they [START] put me in and left me there. Just to assure me that I was comfortable selecting the right place [for me]. I probably could have picked the first option [accommodation in another location] but it wouldn't have worked out [for me]...I felt more involved” (Service User 5).

The process surrounding securing suitable START accommodation was reported by one Service User as “worth the wait” as the location of the accommodation made it easier for [the Service User's] children to visit, which was of particular importance to them:

“They [START team] kept working for a few months trying to find suitable accommodation [within close proximity to children]... a house came up but it wasn't suitable it was too far away... and next thing another one came up...and it was great like...” (Service Users 8).

Another Service User commented on how the START Team took into consideration the need to accommodate a pet and how the team worked to find appropriate accommodation to facilitate this requirement:

“...they could have easily offered me an apartment or absolutely anything. They [START Team] took into consideration how much like how much I need [the dog] and also how much [the dog] has helped me also and I am so grateful for that. I could never be more grateful because they actually gave me thought” (Service User 2).

The role of the Housing Support Worker

All Service Users spoke favourably of the support received from the Housing Support Worker (HSW) and it was evident from the transcripts that such support was instrumental in enabling them to successfully transition to independent living accommodation, promoting individual recovery. HSWs

were described as “legends”, “nicest person I know”, “professional”, “friendly”, “approachable”, “genuine” and “reliable”; their support was described as “excellent”.

The removal/ reduction of HSW support after 12 months was discussed, with the majority calling for sustained HSW support long term, or on an individual needs basis. None of the Service Users reported the need for any changes in terms of support received from the HSW and there were no reports by Service Users in relation to difficulties in contacting their HSW.

It was clear that the support provided by the HSW was essential in enabling Service Users to engage in activities for daily living (ADLs). Most Service Users were able to complete many independent living skills themselves but the effects of their illnesses and living situations prior to their transition were disabling. Being supported, through various dimensions of advocacy, enhanced the development of their confidence, reducing anxiety and enabling the completion of independent living tasks necessary for maintaining a tenancy. The centrality of good care, relationship and collaboration to enabling change was further reported as being essential to the advocacy approach provided by the HSW role.

The advocacy dimensions to the Housing Support Worker Role

The advocacy dimension to the HSW role involved enabling Service Users to access resources to support their tenancies and enhance their inclusion in the community and their recovery. Some of the Service Users reported that their HSW worker signposted them to necessary statutory or community services. Examples included the Back- to -Education Allowance and the various entitlements and benefits from the Department of Social Protection, such as household benefits and packages schemes. One Service User reported that the HSW helped increase their capacity to look after themselves by linking them to support services;

“[HSW] put me in touch with, like, other mental health places like the [name of MH support service] and the [name of MH support service] to help better myself...” (Service User 4).

All Service Users were in agreement that the HSW helped to improve their capacity to look after themselves. Further explanatory discussion evoked responses such as, the HSW guiding them in their “journey” through the START Programme, and there was a sense of “growth”, “development” and an increased sense of wellbeing and self-belief:

“... common sense and looking after your head [HSW] was very good to me” (Service User 1).

“... [HSW] helped me a lot. [HSW] helped me in a lot of ways, like you know a way a person can plant a little seed in your head. , [HSW] guides me like... gives me that thing and actually believe in myself, [HSW] helped me to get my confidence back, doing the small

things you know the way someone could like plant a little seed, as in say something to you and then it'll stick in your head and then all of a sudden it starts to [make sense] and that's what [HSW] did do...helped me a lot, not because they feel they have to but they [HSW] go above and beyond because they [HSW] want to see you succeed, they want you to have like a good opportunity" (Service User 2).

The advocacy dimension of the HSW involved enhancing Service Users' problem-solving skills and confidence levels:

"...before [START Programme and HSW] I wouldn't have [had the confidence to be able to advocate for myself] I would say no, I won't say anything, I'd put it off, but now I'm like no I can do it [I can advocate for myself]." (Service User 2).

The Housing Support Worker and the development of social capital

Service Users described how the HSW also helped to enhance their social capital and inclusion in the wider community whereby the HSW signposted, encouraged and assisted some Service Users to engage (re-engage) with education, training and employment opportunities:

"HSW worker helped me get into [training]- , then I had something to do with my day I have courses to do, you know, I kept my mind busy and active like" (Service User 4).

Another Service User reported that the HSW had encouraged her to upskill and to participate in training, and because of this conversation the service user reported:

"...that kind of stuff [conversations and support] opened up my mind a little bit. You know time is passing by, why don't I go and do something with my life so I started course [named course] in February. So, I passed that and now I am doing a diploma in [another course]. So I've got a few more case studies and I'll have them passed too. And then hopefully, I will go along and do another course" (Service User 2).

Other Service Users reported completing workshops / training on areas relating to mental health including coping strategies and management (Service User 4). One Service User started engaging in third level education at the time of the study and reported that the HSW had supported this process when required (Service User 1).

A small number of Service Users reported successfully securing employment opportunities as result of support received from the HSW;

"[HSW] helped me with doing my CV and applying for a part time job in [name of Department Store], which I got and I am delighted" (Service User 6).

Two Service Users reported that their HSW supported/ encouraged them to access voluntary employment. However due to limited opportunities in the area and concerns over enduring mental health challenges, no suitable voluntary employment opportunities have been identified (Service Users 7&8). One Service User is currently engaged in voluntary employment having been previously involved in training/education. Other Service Users spoke of previously engaging in training courses they did not complete. This particular Service User spoke of not liking “change” or working with “groups”;

“When you have tried different courses before and tried different things. And when you keep telling people it is not going to work out because when you stick it out for three weeks or there for 9 months it’s just not of benefit to me” (Service User 5).

This indicates how the support worker is respectful of Service Users’ individual choices.

Some Service Users reported that the HSW encouraged community integration, encouraging them to meet new people and to access local community programmes e.g., Men’s Shed. Service Users reported they received support to integrate into their new community and described such support in terms of going for walks in their local areas. One Service User described that making new friends and connections was something that was natural to him/her, and thus didn’t require such support: *“I would be pretty outgoing myself so I wouldn’t need that level of support like you know” (Service User 3).*

The majority of Service Users, however, reported that they didn’t fully integrate into their new community, despite feeling content in their new neighbourhood. Barriers to integration relating to their mental health were described as:

“I struggle with that kind of stuff I’ve never had an interest in ever like making friends (Service User 2).”

Most of the Service Users moved into their accommodation during or shortly before the Covid pandemic, and some mentioned this during interview as a reason for not seeing their neighbours.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The overall aim of the START Project was to provide and/or sustain secure tenancies with support for mental health Service Users with identified housing and support needs. START's objectives were to provide and/or sustain secure tenancies in high quality accommodation, to promote recovery of Service Users and to develop an evidence-based sustainable model of practice which could/can become embedded in future service delivery. This evaluation, which utilised a case study design with mixed methods in data collection from the key stakeholders, service providers and Service Users, identified that overall, the START project has met its stated aim and objectives.

As of January 2022, there were thirty-five Service Users housed in thirty-four properties, with seven receiving an interim support service, and four on a waiting list pending availability of suitable properties. The START Project has therefore been successful in obtaining secure tenancies that have enabled Service Users to transition from HSE residences and other unsuitable accommodations (often putting them at risk of homelessness) to START tenure with housing support.

The START Project was recognised by the service providers as having benefited the HSE's Mental Health Services in SECH through the identification and development of an alternative and complementary model for mental health housing provision. Service providers reported that the START project led to a reduction in admissions to acute services. They also reported reduced Service User engagement with the MDTs. It is significant that these reductions were attributed to the support received through the role of the START Housing Support Worker.

These positive views of the success of the START Project were also confirmed by the Service Users, through both the questionnaires and individual interviews. When Service Users were asked to rate their satisfaction with accommodation on a 1-10 scale, where 0 = completely dissatisfied and 10 = completely satisfied, satisfaction with current accommodation was significantly higher than previous accommodation (mean 5.2 and mean 8.7). This positivity was also reflected in the open-ended answers where Service Users identified the positive impacts of the START housing and support on their lives and their physical and mental health.

Service Users identified the role of the HSW as a key element of the START Programme's success, providing invaluable inputs in many areas, including practical, emotional and advocacy support and encouraging development of independent living skills and community integration.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The following are the recommendations for the START Programme emerging from this evaluation.

Recommendation 1

Sustain Funding: Sustain and secure funding to enable the continuation and further development of the START Project.

Recommendation 2

Continue the provision of ongoing / long-term support: The current supports, including engagement with Housing Support Workers, provided to START participants need to be continued. The interagency and multidisciplinary collaborative structure provided by the Shared Support meetings (with a template to guide) needs to continue to allow for prioritisation of support needs and tailored support.

Recommendation 3

Maintain and develop the interagency approach: Continue the commitment from key stakeholders to maintain the collaborative working approach.

Recommendation 4

Increase housing capacity for START Programme: The START Project's progression is hindered by a lack of available housing stock. This highlights the need for both long and short-term planning for housing stock informed by data on housing need among mental health Service Users. An interagency approach to the collection and review of this data is recommended, to ensure accurate information on the location, size and type of housing required going.

Recommendation 5

Review START operational processes: Progress and develop ongoing project review mechanisms and develop additional contingencies to meet emerging challenges.

Recommendation 6

Increase staff capacity and services involved in the START Programme: The value of the project has been confirmed by all stakeholders, with positive impacts seen for the Service Users. Increased capacity would serve to benefit more Service Users.

Recommendation 7

Ensure training on the START Project is provided where necessary: This is particularly relevant if new staff are becoming involved in the START Project and to ensure a trauma-informed understanding of Service Users' needs across all stakeholder groups.

Recommendation 8

Increase support and supervision for Housing Support Workers particularly in relation to mental health challenges: The need for this support emerged through the findings and would help the HSW to meet the Service Users' diverse and often complex needs.

Recommendation 9

Prioritize consideration of the housing and support needs of those living in HSE mental health residences: This is important given the role that the START Project has been playing in the implementation of the National Housing Strategies for People with Disabilities.

Recommendation 10

Adopt a flexible, person centred and needs-based approach to allocation considerations: This may override other criteria, such as length of time on list, in certain circumstances.

Recommendation 11

Develop a protocol to work in collaboration with Housing First and other homeless services: This may help ensure that the most suitable programmes supporting housing for Mental Health Service Users are in place.

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Appendix: List of Abbreviations

AHB	Approved Housing Body
CC	County Council
CHO	Community Health Organisation
HIG	Housing Implementation Group
HSE	Health Service Executive
HSW	Housing Support Worker
LA	Local Authority
MDT	Multi-disciplinary Team
MH	Mental Health
PMHC	Project Manager for Housing Co-ordination
SECH	South East Community Healthcare
SEO	Senior Executive Officer
SRF	Service Reform Fund

